

Bodies as rhetorical devices in Salimbene de Adam's Cronica: The case of Alberico Da Romano

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Abstract

As an experienced narrator, Salimbene de Adam (d. 1288) presents himself as a neutral author while constructing, in his chronicle, a sort of anti-hagiography of the Ghibelline lord Alberico da Romano (d. 1260). Utilising the recurring metaphor of the body, Salimbene delineates an interplay of intertextual references. By analysing and unravelling this narrative, I show the manifold meanings that could be contained within the metaphor of the body in the Middle Ages, spanning through all the stages of the spectrum which goes from sacred to profane, and revealing the techniques employed by the author to manipulate the reactions of his audience.

Keywords: Narratology – Salimbene de Adam – Alberico da Romano – Bodies – Middle Ages

Introduction

Due to the close relationship between human bodies and the personhood they externally manifest, narratives focusing on bodies hold significant power and versatility. Authors, throughout history and into the present, have depicted and narrated bodies to construct and communicate their discourses to a targeted audience. A prime example of this can be found in the opening of Michel Foucault's *Discipline and Punish*, which recounts with gruesome details the 18th-century execution of Robert-François Damiens for his attempted assassination of king Louis XV.⁵⁵⁰ Few other scenes could have enabled Foucault to captivate and impact readers so profoundly, whilst simultaneously exemplifying his conception of physical punishment in the *ancien régime*. Similarly, pre-modern authors frequently employed bodies within their texts as conceptual frameworks, navigating across a thematic spectrum that includes the sacred, the secular, and even the grotesque.⁵⁵¹

Owing to the narrative and rhetorical versatility inherent in the concept of “bodies,” historians can fruitfully examine texts which describe them, in order to gain insights into the mentalities of the respective authors, as well as to understand the broader socio-cultural contexts from which these works emerged.

An ideal example to demonstrate this theory is found in Salimbene de Adam's *Cronica*, penned around the 1280s.⁵⁵² An Italian Franciscan friar, Salimbene composed his chronicle with a focus on the historical events of Northern Italy, particularly underscoring the conflicts between the imperial and ecclesiastical factions, also known as Ghibellines and Guelphs, respectively. He predominantly conveys a viewpoint that favours the latter faction.⁵⁵³ Unfortunately, no other works by Salimbene survived, and even the *Cronica* itself is incomplete, with its initial sections missing. Nevertheless, in the part that survives, this chronicle provides an account of events spanning from 1168 to 1287.⁵⁵⁴

⁵⁵⁰ Michel Foucault, *Discipline and Punish: The Birth of the Prison*, trans. Alan Sheridan (New York: Vintage Books, 1995). The description of the execution takes place on pp. 3–6.

⁵⁵¹ An extensive scholarly work dealing with the importance in the middle ages of the holy relics and of the sacred bodies they represented is Patrick J. Geary's *Furta Sacra: Thefts of Relics in the Central Middle Ages* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1991). The grotesque aspect of the bodily metaphor, linked especially to descriptions of bodily fluids, has instead been analysed by Mikhail Bakhtin in his seminal work *Rabelais and His World*, trans. Helene Iswolsky (Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 1984).

⁵⁵² For an in-depth biography of Salimbene please refer to Enrico Menestò, “La figura di Salimbene de Adam,” in *Salimbene de Adam e la “Cronica”* (Spoleto: Fondazione CISAM, 2018), 1–20. It is worth noting that, while the final entries in the *Cronica* date back to 1287, the year prior to his death, Salimbene likely dedicated many years of his life to this composition, possibly incorporating even earlier writings into the final work.

⁵⁵³ Menestò, “La figura di Salimbene de Adam,” 7.

⁵⁵⁴ Menestò, “La figura di Salimbene de Adam,” 5–6.

As a Franciscan friar, Salimbene was also a preacher, and he displays his narrative expertise in the extensive digressions he takes in the midst of his annalistic narration.⁵⁵⁵ In one such digression, he delves into the story of Alberico Da Romano, the Ghibelline lord of Treviso and a staunch adversary of the ecclesiastical faction.⁵⁵⁶ Whilst Salimbene frequently asserts his own neutrality as a historian, it becomes apparent that he skilfully manoeuvres the narration to convince the audience of Alberico's malevolent character, thus subtly aligning his account with the propagandistic efforts of the ecclesiastical faction.⁵⁵⁷

In the following analysis, I adhere to the sequence of Salimbene's narration as presented in the *Cronica*, augmenting it with my own commentary and contextualisation. My goal is to trace the process by which the author, an expert narrator as I will show, constructs his discourse, and to speculate on the meanings Salimbene might have attempted to convey and the reactions he likely expected to provoke in his audience.⁵⁵⁸

My work is particularly indebted to two scholarly papers published by Claudia Sebastiana Nobili, which dissect the narrative strategies employed by Salimbene.⁵⁵⁹ Notably, Nobili underscores how Ezzelino Da Romano (d. 1259), Alberico's brother, is portrayed by Salimbene as in opposition to Francis of Assisi, providing a stark contrast to both characters. By observing this rhetorical construction, Nobili highlights how Salimbene's narration is deliberately and carefully weighted to ensure that the audience perceives Ezzelino as genuinely evil.⁵⁶⁰

The narrative regarding Alberico appears to pursue a similar goal to that of Ezzelino, but is notably more focused and confined to just a few pages. I also posit that Salimbene's portrayal of Alberico not only serves its own purpose, but also plays a crucial role in further contributing to the development of the characterization of his brother, Ezzelino. This aspect of the narrative, however, is elaborated upon towards the conclusion of this paper.

⁵⁵⁵ Pascale Bourgain, "Langue et style chez Salimbene, entre prétentions savantes et spontanéité," in *Salimbene de Adam e la "Cronica,"* 149.

⁵⁵⁶ Alberico Da Romano, a descendant of a noble Northern Italian family aligned with the imperial cause, served as the podesta of Treviso and died in 1260. The entirety of the story of Alberico analysed is edited in Salimbene de Adam, *Cronica*, ed. Giuseppe Scalia (Bari: Laterza, 1966), 528–533. For his biography, see Dario Canzian, "Romano, Alberico da," in *Dizionario Biografico degli Italiani* (Rome: Istituto dell'Enciclopedia Italiana, 2017).

⁵⁵⁷ On Salimbene's professed neutrality please refer to Claudia Sebastiana Nobili, "La Cronica e la pluralità dei generi letterari," in *Salimbene de Adam e la "Cronica,"* 236.

⁵⁵⁸ In this paper I use the term "audience" rather than "readers" to underscore that medieval books were usually read out aloud, sometimes in the presence of the very author who would clarify any doubts regarding their content. Therefore, they were not just directed at those who could read. Salimbene himself illustrates this process in his *Cronica*, at p. 298, when he describes the Franciscan friar Giovanni da Pian del Carpine who "wrote a great book [...] and he had that book read, as I heard and saw several times [...] and when those who read marveled or did not understand, he would explain and discuss the individual things" ([S]cripsit unum magnum librum [...] et faciebat illum librum legi, ut pluries audivi et vidi [...] et ubi mirabantur vel non intelligebant legentes, ipse exponebat et disserebat de singulis).

⁵⁵⁹ These are: Claudia Sebastiana Nobili, "La costruzione del personaggio fra letteratura e storia: Salimbene da Parma e Dante," in *La letteratura e la storia*, eds. Elisabetta Menetti and Carlo Varotti (Bologna: Gedit, 2007), 315–336; and Nobili, "La Cronica e la pluralità dei generi letterari," 233–250.

⁵⁶⁰ Nobili, "La Cronica e la pluralità dei generi letterari."

Salimbene introduces Alberico Da Romano in the course of his narration and in a subtle way, almost in passing. In a specific paragraph, he lists the lords who reigned in the regions of Lombardy and Romagna. However, while all the other noblemen are merely mentioned by their name, Salimbene elaborates on Alberico with an extended commentary, writing that this imperial vicar and podesta of Treviso was a true *membrum diaboli*, just like his brother Ezzelino, and that for this reason, he met a tragic fate, along with his wife and his offspring.⁵⁶¹ The epithet *membrum diaboli* is the first bodily metaphor in this narration and literally translates to “a piece of the devil’s body,” an expression which in the context of medieval literature could imply an act of “conscious separation from the body of Christ through sin.”⁵⁶²

The Execution

Following this introduction, Salimbene describes the death of both Alberico and his family. He narrates a harrowing scene where the people of Treviso, after having captured their former podesta, tore off the limbs of his sons and used them to strike his face.⁵⁶³ I suggest that in this, as in other passages, Salimbene considers the entire family as an extension of Alberico’s body. Indeed, the notion of a collective familial body is reinforced in a later passage, when Salimbene states that Alberico’s family was doomed to suffer because of the sins of its patriarch.⁵⁶⁴ The specific manner in which Salimbene chooses to motivate the fate of the other members of the Da Romano family suggests that he views them as fundamentally intertwined with, and enduring the consequences of, Alberico’s own actions, while also implying that their suffering is not separate, but an extension of the punishment meted out to Alberico himself. The motif of collective identity and of familial fate tied to that of the patriarch is, after all, a recurring element in the analysed narration, which will be explored in greater detail further on in the paper. Thus, the act of the sons’ limbs striking the father would mainly symbolise the metaphorical body of Alberico’s family as in revolt against itself.

Subsequently, Salimbene describes the burning at the stake of Alberico’s wife and of his daughters. The young girls, in particular, are described as beautiful and innocent, yet still having to share the retribution for their father’s sins. Salimbene’s omission of the names of any other member of the family, except for Alberico’s, further strips them of their individual identities, rendering them once again as a mere extension of Alberico’s persona. The climax of this tragic

⁵⁶¹ Salimbene, *Cronica*, 528.

⁵⁶² Gustav Zamore, “A peripheral Heretic? An Early Fourteenth-Century Heresy Trial from Sweden,” *Historical Research* 93, no. 262 (November 2020): 614, footnote 76.

⁵⁶³ Salimbene, *Cronica*, 528.

⁵⁶⁴ Salimbene, *Cronica*, 531, where the Venetians call for the death of Alberico and his family. Additionally, for a more comprehensive analysis of this incident and its implications, please refer to the section titled “The Crusade” in this paper.

episode has the people of Treviso gruesomely tearing away Alberico's flesh with pincers, until his entire body was "destroyed with mockery, infamy and terrible torment."⁵⁶⁵

Whilst Salimbene's account of this public execution provides a detailed depiction, it is not the sole contemporary record of these events. The chronicler Rolandino of Padova (d. 1276) too recounts the final moments of Alberico's life. In contrast to Salimbene's account, Rolandino provides the names of Alberico's wife and sons, and Alberico himself is humanised by being portrayed as hoping for his family's survival, so that they could have perpetuated his lineage. Notably, Rolandino also recounts the final act of mercy granted to Alberico by his executioners: to have the restraints on his mouth removed to allow him to confess and receive an absolution from a Franciscan friar present at the scene. On the other hand, Rolandino's description of the execution itself lacks the extensive and gruesome detail found in Salimbene's version.⁵⁶⁶

It is plausible that Salimbene was aware of these events, as he too references Alberico's final act of repentance. However, he chooses to mention this detail only after concluding the main narrative, which is predominantly focused on Alberico's crimes and punishment.⁵⁶⁷ This structuring suggests that Salimbene's primary intention was to underscore the gravity of Alberico's transgressions and the consequent retribution, with the acknowledgement of his repentance serving only as a secondary note.

Alberico's gory death brings to mind the already mentioned execution of Robert-François Damiens as recounted by Foucault: Alberico's body too is "effaced, [...] destroyed piece by piece," and here too an institutional authority decrees a death sentence and the manner of its implementation.⁵⁶⁸ Salimbene characterizes the wrath of the citizens as divine retribution which he justifies by listing the crimes that Alberico committed: he killed many of their relatives, and he asked for too many tributes. Furthermore, according to Salimbene, Alberico feigned a war against his brother Ezzelino to steal and destroy even more than he was already doing.⁵⁶⁹ Thus, through the "infinitesimal destruction of the body" of Alberico and his family, the tyrant's power is also destroyed.⁵⁷⁰ The intention to delete Alberico's power by annihilating his family is probably what

⁵⁶⁵ "[E]t sic destruxerunt corpus eius ludibriis et opprobriis et gravibus tormentis," Salimbene, *Cronica*, 528.

⁵⁶⁶ Rolandino of Padova, "De factis in Marchia Tarvisina libri XII," ed. Felice Osio in *Rerum Italicarum Scriptores*, ed. Ludovico Antonio Muratori (Milan, Stamperia della Società Palatina: 1726), 8:358.

⁵⁶⁷ Salimbene, *Cronica*, 533. Perhaps Salimbene knew that repentance happened precisely because there were Franciscans witnessing the execution. On the sources used by Salimbene, mainly first-hand accounts by other Franciscan friars, please refer to Nobili, "La costruzione del personaggio," 333.

⁵⁶⁸ The quotation comes from Foucault, *Discipline and Punish*, 50. For the death sentence of Alberico and his family issued by the city of Treviso see Gian Battista Verci ed., "Sententia Marci Badoarii Potestatis Tarvisii contra illos de Romano," in *Storia degli Ecelini* (Bassano: Remondini, 1779), 3:421–423. Both Salimbene's and Rolandino's accounts differ from what was established by this document, according to which the male members of the family were simply to be hanged.

⁵⁶⁹ Salimbene, *Cronica*, 528.

⁵⁷⁰ The quotation comes from Foucault, *Discipline and Punish*, 51.

motivated the actual sentence in the first place, for the connection between those bodies and the power of the da Romano house must have been clear to the citizens of Treviso.⁵⁷¹

The Hanging

According to Nobili's analysis, characters in the *Cronica* can be classified according to their complexity. Some of them are "flat," static, and easily defined with few epithets, while others are "round," dynamic, and during the narration undergo a significant transformation.⁵⁷² Alberico's literary character would certainly fall into the former category, as his whole persona can be summarised in just a few sentences. Salimbene refers to him as "the cursed Alberico," unchanging in his deviancy.⁵⁷³ Yet, a degree of dynamism is still added to the story by reversing the chronological order of events, thanks to progressive flashbacks which set up a climax of depravity, and effectively offer a justification for the brutal execution described at the outset. Therefore, by initially detailing the execution and then methodically revealing Alberico's transgressions, Salimbene first piques the audience's curiosity about the reasons behind such extreme violence, and then satisfies it with a narrative structure which gradually guides towards an understanding and eventual endorsement of his moral condemnation against Alberico.⁵⁷⁴

Salimbene continues the story by recounting that, during his rule as podesta of Treviso, Alberico ordered the execution by hanging of twenty-five prominent men, suspecting them of conspiracy. Additionally, he also intended to mutilate the noses of their female relatives but was dissuaded by the intervention of an unnamed man Alberico believed to be his illegitimate son.⁵⁷⁵ Salimbene points out that this man was not Alberico's actual son, and this clarification might serve a precise function: all those who were related to Alberico ended up participating in his suffering, as if they were part of his own body. Therefore this man, who would later be spared because of his show of piety, could not have been a member of the ill-fated Da Romano lineage, not to break the thematic consistency constructed by the narrative. As the story progresses Alberico, diverging from his initial cruel intention, ordered instead the women's dresses to be cut just above their breasts, leaving them naked below that point, while also subjecting the condemned men to witness this act of humiliation. Such forceful undressing is an ancient and unequivocal method of shaming, particularly for women. In the Bible, this act is likened to the degradation reserved for prostitutes,

⁵⁷¹ Cf. "Sententia contra de Romano," 421–423.

⁵⁷² Nobili, "La costruzione del personaggio," 320.

⁵⁷³ "[M]aledictus Albricus," Salimbene, *Cronica*, 531.

⁵⁷⁴ Cf. Nobili, "La Cronica e la pluralità," 237, 239.

⁵⁷⁵ Salimbene, *Cronica*, 529.

a detail which foreshadows some further elements of the narration, and which connects this passage to the conclusion of Alberico's story.⁵⁷⁶

It has been noted that "the clothed body in medieval literature promotes a civilised social identity."⁵⁷⁷ Salimbene himself links clothing to feminine identity, noting in another, distinct passage of his chronicle the adverse reaction of some noblewomen to sumptuary laws that banned long dresses, a prohibition which, he says, they found "more bitter than death."⁵⁷⁸ Additionally, those same women were forced by law to wear veils on their head, reflecting the contemporary conception that hair was a symbol of feminine sexuality.⁵⁷⁹ Consequently, it is significant that the women humiliated by Alberico retain their headdresses, maintaining a symbol of their still-intact womanly virtue. Yet, their forceful undressing still removes them from the sphere of civilised society, and they lose their social identity, if not for a figment of their dignified self which is implied in their covered hair.⁵⁸⁰

The women, now stripped of their garments, were forced to walk beneath the hanging men, and as they passed, those who were dying struck their relatives with their feet, in their involuntary, final spasms.⁵⁸¹ This scene could be interpreted as a recurring metaphor, symbolically conveying that the women experienced the death of their relatives through their own physical suffering, mirroring the fate of Alberico's family. Additionally, the kicks by their family members that they endure echo the already depicted scene where Alberico is battered with the limbs of his own sons. Salimbene employs these subtle but constant references to Alberico's execution as narrative tools, ensuring that the audience remains engaged and attentive to the thematic thread he unwinds.

Ultimately, the women were abandoned in the wilderness, wearing just the tattered remnants of their garments, which they repurposed to cover their genitalia.⁵⁸² Salimbene draws

⁵⁷⁶ Ez 16:39. In the *New International Version Bible* this passage reads "Then I will deliver you into the hands of your lovers, and they will tear down your mounds and destroy your lofty shrines. They will strip you of your clothes and take your fine jewelry and leave you stark naked." However, in the *Biblia Sacra Vulgata*, the Latin edition of the Bible, this passage is somewhat different: "Et dabo te in manus eorum, et destruent lupanar tuum, et demolientur prostibulum tuum: et denudabunt te vestimentis tuis, et auferent vasa decoris tui, et derelinquent te nudam, plenamque ignominia." Instead of "mounds," here we find the word *lupanar*, which unequivocally means "brothel," establishing a direct association between forceful undressing and prostitution.

⁵⁷⁷ Rihanne Whitney, "Undressing Medieval Bodies: Exploring Sin, Shame and Sexuality through Representations of Nudity and Nakedness in the Middle Ages," (MA thesis, University of Leiden, 2021), 4; cf. Leora Auslander, "Deploying Material Culture to Write the History of Gender and Sexuality: The Example of Clothing and Textiles," *Clio* 40 (2014): 158-159.

⁵⁷⁸ Salimbene, *Cronica*, 246.

⁵⁷⁹ Marian Bleeke, Jennifer Borland, Rachel Dressler, Martha Easton, and Elizabeth L'Estrange, "Artistic Representation: Women and/in Medieval Visual Culture," in *A Cultural History of Women in the Middle Ages*, ed. Kim M. Phillips (London: Bloomsbury 2013), 197.

⁵⁸⁰ Whitney, "Undressing Medieval Bodies," 54.

⁵⁸¹ Salimbene, *Cronica*, 529-530.

⁵⁸² "Operuerunt sibi membra genitalia, id est pudenda," Salimbene, *Cronica*, 530.

poignant parallels between their ordeal and the plights of biblical figures such as Susanna, whose honour was compromised but later restored, and the adulteress whom Jesus saved from stoning.⁵⁸³ Furthermore, he also mentions the prophet Isaiah, who was brutally killed by being sawn in half by soldiers.⁵⁸⁴ These scriptural references serve a dual purpose in Salimbene's narrative. Firstly, they anchor the author's account to revered biblical passages, lending it an aura of authority. Secondly, the mention of these distressed biblical women evokes once again the traumatic experience suffered by the women of Treviso. Additionally, the reference to Isaiah's martyrdom in this passage, and to his body being effaced by his torturers, also serves as a foreboding echo of the grim fate that would befall Alberico. Through these parallels and repetitions, Salimbene effectively sustains and enlivens the prevailing theme of the body.⁵⁸⁵

Monsters on the Shore

Salimbene continues his story by introducing a fisherman who initially mistook the naked women for "illusions of demons, ghosts, or sea monsters."⁵⁸⁶ This association emphasises the profound loss of social identity and human status that has been forced upon the women, who are transfigured into monstrous creatures. Indeed, in the Middle Ages nudity was generally associated with exotic otherness, while being clothed was considered to be the natural state of the socialised human being.⁵⁸⁷ Furthermore, the anxiety for covering exposed genitalia displayed by the women echoes the biblical narrative of the expulsion from Eden, when Adam and Eve found themselves in need to cover their exposed nakedness. This allusion situates the women in a context akin to humanity's fall from grace, symbolically reverting them to what was considered to be the most grievous moment in human history, at least according to the canonical Christian perspective.

The Crusade

The narration continues with the fisherman eventually approaching the women and aiding them in reaching the nearby city of Venice. There, a new character takes the stage: archbishop Ottaviano degli Ubaldini (d. 1273), a papal legate representing the ecclesiastical faction's interests, and an opponent to Alberico, who belonged to the rival faction. Thus, on the following day, Ottaviano gathered the populace in San Marco's square to publicly display the women, still naked as Alberico

⁵⁸³ The first episode refers to the narrative of Susanna and the Elders, in the thirteenth chapter of the Book of Daniel. The episode of the adulteress, instead, comes from John 7:53–8:11.

⁵⁸⁴ The death of Isaiah is not described in the canonical Bible. Instead, Salimbene refers to extrabiblical narrations.

⁵⁸⁵ On the use of repetitions in Salimbene's narratives, please refer to Nobili "La Cronica e la pluralità," 236; Nobili, "La costruzione del personaggio," 320.

⁵⁸⁶ "[I]llusiones demonum seu fantasmata aut certe monstra marina. Horribiliter timuit," Salimbene, *Cronica*, 530.

⁵⁸⁷ Whitney, "Undressing Medieval Bodies," 8, 32, 53.

had left them.⁵⁸⁸ This sight incited a vehement response from the Venetians, who cried out in outrage: “Death, death to that cursed man, and may he be burned alive with his wife and with all his children.”⁵⁸⁹ A crusade was thus proclaimed to avenge the hanging of those men and the shaming of those women, a detail that Salimbene repeats in full, deliberately reminding its significance for his audience.⁵⁹⁰

The promptness of the reaction of the Venetian population demonstrates just how straightforward the outrage generated by such a scene could have been for the medieval public. Nevertheless, as the noblewomen were exposed to everyone’s sight without any regard for their dignity, it is possible that their shame may have lied not so much in nudity per se, but in the violence they endured by being degraded to sub-human status through forceful undressing.⁵⁹¹

The Ultimate Sin

Although the crusade inflicted substantial harm on Alberico, it did not result in his complete defeat, which instead would come at a later point, a fact that Salimbene reminds to an audience which already knows this, thanks to the first part of the narration.

However, to further justify the extreme retribution which led Alberico’s family to be eradicated, Salimbene narrates a final anecdote: once, during a hunt, upon losing his falcon Alberico even dared to show his ass to God in an extreme act of defiance.⁵⁹² Furthermore, upon returning to the city, he committed an even more blasphemous act inside the cathedral: he desecrated the altar by defecating on it, in the very place where the holy host was consecrated.⁵⁹³

Defecation was an unambiguous act of defilement in the Middle Ages,⁵⁹⁴ and Salimbene himself employs the same metaphor elsewhere, when describing a bishop whom he considered to be a grave sinner, recounting that “a dog shat on him after he was buried [...]. He should have been buried in a dunghill.”⁵⁹⁵ While in medieval texts, bodily functions held a comical undertone too, Salimbene seems to be markedly serious in telling of Alberico’s sins.⁵⁹⁶ Any mockery present here

⁵⁸⁸ Salimbene, *Cronica*, 530.

⁵⁸⁹ “Moriatur, moriatur maledictus ille et vivus ardeat cum uxore, et tota eius progenies de hoc seculo extirpetur,” Salimbene, *Cronica*, 531.

⁵⁹⁰ Cf. Nobili, “La Cronica e la pluralità,” 244.

⁵⁹¹ Cf. Whitney, “Undressing Medieval Bodies,” 10, 34.

⁵⁹² “[C]um tota sua progenie penitus est deletus [...]. [E]xtraxit sibi bracas et culum ostendit Deo in signum opprobrii et convitii atque derisionis,” Salimbene, *Cronica*, 532.

⁵⁹³ “[C]accavit super altare, in eo loco proprie ubi consecratur Dominicum corpus.” Salimbene, *Cronica*, 532.

⁵⁹⁴ Bakhtin, *Rabelais and His World*, 147-48.

⁵⁹⁵ “[E]t scio quod canis cacavit super eum, postquam sepultus fuit [...]. Revera dignus erat in sterquilinum sepeliri,” Salimbene, *Cronica*, 758.

⁵⁹⁶ On the comical undertone of bodily functions please refer to Bakhtin, *Rabelais and His World*, 151-52.

is directed not at the act itself, but at Alberico's audacity in assuming that he could have behaved in such a way towards God without suffering any consequence.⁵⁹⁷

Finally, and to reinforce this anti-hagiography with one last detail, Salimbene further adds that Alberico's wife used to call other noblewomen "whores and harlots," a behaviour that her husband did not challenge.⁵⁹⁸ The accusation implied towards Alberico here seems to be that of failing to adhere to the societal expectation of maintaining order within his household, flouting the established gender norms. Additionally, this account provides an additional reference to the treatment that Alberico reserved for the women from Treviso: he treated them like prostitutes, and his wife proves to be no different, even if only through words. Thus, even with this last passage, Salimbene ensures that the audience fully grasps the intended moral condemnation towards Alberico.

The Body of Christ and the Body of the Devil

Alberico's act of desecration against what was considered to be the holiest of relics, the eucharist, could be interpreted in relation to the epithet *membrum diaboli* assigned to him at the beginning of the story. This couple of words set up a critical juxtaposition: rather than partaking in the holy communion and becoming one with Christ, a member of His body, Alberico defiles the holy host and becomes a member of the body of Christ's enemy, as if he had performed a perverse inversion of the communion ritual.⁵⁹⁹

Thus, the narrative arc reaches its culmination with Alberico's ultimate sin against the body of Christ, representing the gravest possible transgression. Consequently, Alberico pays the price for his actions with his own body. In a metaphorical replication of his own rebellion against the Eternal Father, he also experiences torment by being struck by the limbs of his own sons. The recurrence with which the same images are repeated demonstrates a deliberate intent on Salimbene's part in weaving a coherent narrative rich in internal references.⁶⁰⁰

⁵⁹⁷ I capitalise the initial letter of God and referrants to him here and elsewhere out of my personal convictions.

⁵⁹⁸ "[D]ominas et matronas appellabat putanas et meretrices." Salimbene, *Cronica*, 532.

⁵⁹⁹ Cf. Zamore, "A peripheral Heretic?" 614: "Instead of becoming a member of the body of Christ through consuming the consecrated host, Botulf has, through 'vomiting forth his error,' become a member of the body of the Devil, separated from the body of the faithful."

⁶⁰⁰ Nobili, "La costruzione del personaggio," 329.

The Repenting and the Tale of Ezzelino

Contrasting with the extensive narrative dedicated to the more (in)famous Ezzelino, the account on Alberico is confined to just a few pages, and his name is scarcely mentioned elsewhere in the *Cronica*, as if the obliteration of his body had been so absolute that not even his memory had survived it. However, it is likely that Salimbene's primary purpose in introducing Alberico in these pages is to set the stage for the subsequent account of Ezzelino, providing a term of comparison to magnify the enormity of the latter's crimes: while Alberico hanged twenty-five men, Ezzelino burned 11,000 men in a single day.⁶⁰¹ Moreover, while Alberico repented just before his death, Ezzelino persisted in his wickedness until the end.⁶⁰² This stark contrast is seemingly designed to impress upon the audience that Alberico's tale is merely a prelude to the truly heinous character of his brother, thereby amplifying anticipation for the ensuing passages about Ezzelino.

As Ezzelino's story takes the stage, Alberico fades into the background and is never referred to again, despite having, in reality, outlived his brother. The fleeting mention to Alberico's repentance suggests that Salimbene was likely aware of more than he chose to disclose, probably owing to the testimony of the Franciscans who, according to Rolandino of Padova, were present at the execution. Salimbene's selective narration can be interpreted as a deliberate decision to avoid humanizing Alberico, in order to maintain the moral thrust of his tale. Thus, the nuanced tragicity of Alberico's character as depicted by Rolandino finds no place in Salimbene's chronicle.

⁶⁰¹ Salimbene, *Cronica*, 533.

⁶⁰² "However, upon his death, Alberico completely repented, while Ezzelino never went back to God" (Verumtamen in morte Albricus optime fuit contritus. Icilius vero nunquam est reversus ad Deum). Salimbene, *Cronica*, 533.

Conclusion

In this concise segment of his narrative, Salimbene demonstrates a masterful use of the metaphor of the body, imbuing it with multifaceted meanings. Alberico atones for his sins with his own body, a body which is also a symbol of power and that grows to encompass his entire family, unifying them as a singular entity. Furthermore, I have highlighted how forced undressing, but not necessarily nudity itself, could have been associated with humiliation and degradation in this particular context. Finally, Salimbene also uses the metaphor of the body to stage an intricate and allegorical perversion of the communion in the body of Christ.

These thematic elements are hardly coincidental; each aspect is carefully interwoven with the others, creating a complex tapestry of cross-references that engage the audience and subtly direct their moral discernment.⁶⁰³ Consequently, Salimbene's account is fictionalised at least to some extent, as it is strategically crafted to influence the audience's ethical conclusions, demonstrating in the process the prowess of the author as a storyteller, as well as his astute comprehension of the body as a potent rhetorical device.⁶⁰⁴

⁶⁰³ Nobili "La Cronica e la pluralità," 242, 246.

⁶⁰⁴ Nobili "La Cronica e la pluralità," 250; and Nobili, "La costruzione del personaggio," 330.

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